

DESIGN SUSTAINED RELEASE BI-LAYER TABLET OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUG FOR IMPROVED DRUG DELIVERY

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Article Received on 25 March 2026,
Article Revised on 16 April 2026,
Article Published on 01 May 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19875363>

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How To Cite This Article: Shrinivas Rajesh Shinde*, Dr. P. M. Pimpalshende. (2026). Design Sustained Release Bi-Layer Tablet of Antihypertensive Drug for Improved Drug Delivery. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(5), 141-169.
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ABSTRACT

The aim of present study is to design sustained release Bilayer tablet of Antihypertensive drug for improved drug delivery. To develop stable formulation of Antihypertensive drugs. To develop improved beneficial technology to overcome the shortcoming of the single tablet. To design modified release drug product for optimization of therapeutic regimen. To ensure safety and to improve efficacy of drug as well as patient compliance. To study the effect of concentration of polymer on drug release. Evaluation of precompression parameters such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density. The oral route is the most popular route used for administration of drugs, which is due in part to the ease of administration and to the fact that gastrointestinal physiology offers more flexibility in dosage form design than most other routes¹. The term sustained release, prolonged release, modified release, extended release,

or depot formulation are used to identify drugs delivery systems that are designed to achieve or extended therapeutic effect by continuously releasing medication over an extended period of time after administration of a single dose. Bilayer tablets can be primary option to avoid chemical incompatibilities between APIs by physical separation and to enable the development of different drug release profiles. Bilayer tablet is suitable for sequential release of two drugs in combination and also for sustained release of tablet in which one layer is for immediate release as loading dose and second layer is maintenance dose. So use of bilayer tablets is a very different aspect for antihypertensive, diabetic, antiinflammatory and analgesic drugs where combination therapy is often used. Several pharmaceutical companies are currently developing bilayer tablets, for a variety of reasons: patent extension,

therapeutic, marketing to name a few. Generally, tablets manufacturing principles remain the same, there is much more to consider because making multilayer tablets involves multiple often incompatible products, additional equipment and many formulation and operation challenges.

KEYWORD: Post-compression test, Pre-compression test, Antihypertensive drug, Immediate release, Bilayer tablet.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustained release drug delivery system

Generally speaking, tablet production principles are the same, but there are many more factors to take into account because creating multilayer tablets requires numerous, frequently incompatible goods, extra equipment, and several formulation and operating issues. Any medication or dose form with a sustained release (SR) pattern prolongs the medication's therapeutic action.

Sustained release formulations aim to release the medication at a predefined rate for the intended duration.

A sustained release system where the dosage forms regulate the drug's rate of appearance in the body rather than the biological absorption process.

To achieve a therapeutic level quickly and sustained the level for a given period of time, the dosage forms generally consist of two dosage

- (1) Loading dosage (D_i) = it gives burst release
- (2) Maintenance dose (D_m) = it maintains the drug
- (3) Concentration in plasma gives sustained effect.

$$\text{Total dosage } = W = D_i + D_m \quad (1)$$

$$W = D_i + K_r0 T_d \quad (2)$$

Where K_r0 is the zero order rate constant for drug release and T_d is the total time desired for sustained release from one dose.

If D_m begins the release of drug at the time of dosing ($t = 0$)

$$W = D_i + K_r0 T_d - K_r0 T_p \quad (3)$$

T_p the time of peak plasma level

Correlation factor $K_r0 T_p$ is the amount of drug provided during the period from $t = 0$ the time

of peak drug level T_p .

The total dose of such a system is

$$W = D_i + (K_e C_d / K_r) V_d \tag{4}$$

K_r = Rate constant of first order drug release

If DM begins releasing drug at $t = 0$ a correlation factor is required the correct expression is

$$W = D_i + (K C_d / C_r) v_d - K_r T_p \tag{5}$$

(Figure No. 1) shows ideal plasma concentration curves for immediate release (IR), zero order release (ZODDS), So to maintain a constant drug level the rate of drug absorption should be equal to the rate of elimination³⁻⁴.

Fig no.1 Ideal plasma concentration curves for immediate release, zero order release and sustained release drug delivery system.

1. Drug Delivery System with Sustained Release

- Made to keep medication levels in the blood steady throughout time.
- Replicates a continuous intravenous infusion (drug input equals drug elimination).

Fig. no.2 Plasma drug concentration versus time for zero order controlled release, sustained release and release from conventional dosage forms.

• Applications

Loading dose (D_i): quick initial impact

Maintenance dosage (D_m): keeps the medication level stable.

- The objective is to maintain a constant therapeutic focus and prevent oscillations.

Advantages

- Less frequent dosing

Improved adherence to treatment

- Consistent medication levels in the blood
- Less adverse effects.

Disadvantages

- Increased price
- Challenging dose modification
- Drug action cannot be swiftly stopped
- Unsuitable for medications with a limited window of absorption

2. Tablets (General) Benefits

- Precise dosage and affordable
- Simple to manufacture, handle, and transport
- Excellent microbiological and chemical stability

Disadvantages

- Certain medications are difficult to compress.
- A coating may be necessary if it is poorly soluble or tastes awful.
- In certain situations, it might lower bioavailability

3. Tablets with Immediate Release (IR)

- Quick drug release and breakdown following administration
- Offer prompt action

Perfect Properties

- Quick dissolution
- Delicious flavor and mouthfeel • Stable and simple to produce

Advantages

- Quick action Elevated bioavailability

- Convenient and economical drawbacks
- Needs to be taken frequently
- Danger of elevated plasma concentration → poisoning

4. Tablets with Extended Release (ER)

- The medication is released gradually over extended periods of time (up to 24 hours).
- Boost bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy.

Important Drug Selection Factors

The solubility is moderate.

- Consistent in the GI system
- An appropriate molecular size
- Not strongly attached to proteins
- Throughout the GI tract, absorbed

Types of Extended release formulation

Many current oral extended release systems are available

1. Dissolution-controlled release system.
2. Diffusion-controlled release system.
3. Osmotic pump system.
4. Erosion controlled release systems.

5. Tablets with two layers Bilayer Tablets

- Have two drug layers, such as immediate and sustained release.
- Applied to controlled release or combination Therapy.

Advantages

- Keep incompatible medications apart
- Regulate the rates of discharge
- Boost the efficacy of treatment

Bilayer tablet Challenges

- Separation of layers
- Variation in weight
- Complexity of manufacturing

6. High blood pressure, or Hypertension

- $\geq 140/90$ mmHg is the definition.
- Referred to be a "silent killer" since it frequently shows no symptoms

Types Hypertension

1. Crucial (most prevalent)
2. Secondary (caused by illness)
3. Malignant (extreme)
4. Pregnancy-related
5. Clinical anxiety, or white-coat

Complications in Hypertension

- Heart conditions
- A stroke
- Management of kidney damage
- Modifications to lifestyle:

Cut salt intake in half, Regular exercise, weight maintenance, and abstinence from smoking

The aim of present study is to design sustained release Bi-layer tablet of Antihypertensive drug for improved drug delivery.

Objective

To develop stable formulation of Antihypertensive drugs.

Evaluation of pre-compression parameters such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped Density, Carr's index and Hauser's ratio.

Evaluation of post-compression parameters such as weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, drug content, in-vitro drug release studies and in-vitro release kinetics studies.

MATERIAL

Various material were used to carry out the experimental work. The list of material used are given in the table no.1

Table no. 1: List of material used in formulation.

Sr. No.	Material	Sources
1.	Propranolol	Concept pharma Aurangabad
2.	HPMC-15 m	Zim laboratories Ltd, Nagpur
3.	Microcrystalline cellulose	S.D fine chem limited, Mumbai

4.	Ethyl cellulose	Loba chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
5.	HPMC-100 C	S.D fine chem limited, Mumbai
6.	Sodium starch glycolate	Loba chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai
7.	Polyvinyl-pyrrolidone	S.D fine chem limited, Mumbai
8.	Mg. stearate	Zim laboratories Ltd, Nagpur
9.	Talc	S.D fine chem limited, Mumbai

METHODS

A. Pre-formulation study

1. Organoleptic properties:

i. Color: A small quantity of propranolol HCL powders were taken in butter paper and viewed in well-illuminated place.

ii. Taste and odour: Very less quantity of propranolol HCL was used to get taste with the help of tongue as well as smelled to get the odour.

2. Physical characteristics: Loss on Drying

Determined on 1.000 g by drying in an oven at 100°C to 105°C for 3 hours. Mix and accurately weigh the substance to be tested. Solubility Analysis:

1) Solubility: Solvents such as Methanol, alcohol and water and isopropyl alcohol are used for the solubility studies.

Descriptive Term	Parts of Solvent Required for 1 part of Solute
Very soluble	Less than 1
Freely soluble	From 1 to 10
Soluble	From 10 to 30
Sparingly soluble	From 30 to 100
Slightly soluble	From 100 to 1,000
Very slightly soluble	From 1,000 to 10,000
Practically insoluble or Insoluble	Greater than or equal to 10,000

2) pH of the solution

Dissolved 6.50 gm of propranolol HCL in purified water and finally makes the volume up to 100 ml with purified water. Read the pH of that solution with the help of pH meter.

3) Melting point

Melting points of propranolol HCL were determined, by taking the drug sample in small amount in a capillary tube closed at one end. Capillary tube containing drug was placed in melting point equipment. The temperature at which the drug started melting and becomes liquid was noted.

4) Partition coefficient

The partition coefficient study of propranolol HCL was performed using noctanol as the organic phase and distilled water as the aqueous phase. drug concentration in aqueous phase and noctanol phases was determined spectrophotometrically Results are shown.

5) Flow properties (Angle of Repose)

The angle of repose of granules was determined by funnel method.. The angle of repose was calculated by using equation.

$$\tan \theta = h/r \quad (\text{or}) \quad \theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$$

Where, h and r are the height and radius of the powder cone.

Table No: 2 Angle of repose as an indication of granule flow properties.

Angle of repose (°)	Type of flow
<25	Excellent
25 – 30	Good
30 - 40	Poor
>40	Very poor

a) Bulk density: (Db)Procedure:

Weighed quantity of Propranolol HCL were transferred into a 50ml measuring cylinder without tapping during transfer the volume occupied by granules was measured.

Bulk density (Db) was measured by using formula.

$$D_b = m/V_o$$

Where, m: Mass of the blend, vo: Untapped Volume

b) Tapped density: (Dt) Procedure

Weighed quantity of Propranolol was taken into a graduated cylinder, volume occupied by granules was noted down. Then cylinder was subjected to 500/ 750 and 1250 taps in tapped density tester (Electro Lab USPII) According to USP, the blend was subjected for 500 taps the % Volume variation was calculated by following formula.

$$D_t = m/V_i$$

Where, m: Mass of the blend Vi: Tapped Volume

c) Measurement of Powder Compressibility

i. Compressibility Index

Table No: 3 Carr's index as an indication of granule flow properties Tapped density.

Carr's index (%)	Type of flow
5 – 15	Excellent
12 – 16	Good
18 – 21	Fair to passable
23 – 35	Poor
33 – 38	Very poor

The compressibility index of the granules was determined by the Carr's compressibility index.

ii. Determination of Hausner ratio

It is measurement of frictional resistance of the drug. It was determined by the ratio of tapped density and bulk density.

Table No: 4 Hausner's ratio as an indication of granule flow properties.

Flow character	Hausner's ratio
Excellent	1.00 – 1.11
Good	1.12 – 1.18
Fair	1.19 – 1.25
Passable	1.26 – 1.34
Poor	1.35 – 1.45
Very Poor	1.46 – 1.59
Very very Poor	> 1.60

B. Analytical methods

1. Standard curve of propranolol HCL

1) Determination of absorption maxima (λ -max) of propranolol HCL

2) Preparation of standard plot of propranolol HCL in 0.1N HCL (pH1.2)

3) Preparation of standard plot in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8)

4) Preparation of standard plot in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4)

2. Dose calculation:- Half-life of propranolol HCL is 4 hrs.

3. Formulation of sustained release bilayer tablets.

a. Preparation of blends for direct compression and wet granulation method

Composition of immediate release layer and sustained release layer are shown in Table no.5.

Table No: 5 Composition of propranolol HCL immediate release layer.

Sr. No.	Ingredient	IR 1	IR 2	IR 3
1.	Propranolol	25	25	25
2.	S.S.G.	5	7.5	10
3.	Mannitol	60	57.5	55
4.	Aerosil	2.5	2.5	2.5
5.	PVP k30	5	5	5
6.	Mg. sterate	2.5	2.5	2.5
7.	Colorant	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S
	Total.	100	100	100

Table 6: Composition of propranolol HCL sustained release layer.

Sr. no.	Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	PropranololHCL	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55	55
2	Ethyl cellulose	27.5	55	82.5	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	HPMC k15	-	-	-	27.5	55	82.5	-	-	-
4	HPMC 100	-	-	-	-	-	-	27.5	55	82.5
5	MCC	162.5	135	107.5	162.5	135	107.5	162.5	135	107.5
6	Talc	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
7	Mg. stearate	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
	TOTAL	250mg	250 mg							

- 1) Blends preparation of immediate release layer for direct compression method The Propranolol layer was prepared by using direct compression method.
- 2) Blends preparation of sustained release layer for direct compression method Drug and all the excipient except the magnesium stearate were accurately weighed and passed through #80mesh screen.

b. Pre-compression evaluation of blends

1. Bulk density and tapped density

10 gm of blend was taken in 100 ml measuring cylinder. Without troubling the cylinder the volume of powder was noted.

Bulk density (ρ) = Weight of sample /Bulk volume

Tapped density (ρ_b) =Weight of sample /Tapped volume

2. Hausner quotient

Hausner ratio or quotient was calculated as the ratio of tapped to bulk densities.

Hausner's quotient (ratio) =Tapped density /Bulk density

3. Carr's index %

The Carr's index % of blends was calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{Carr's index \%} = \frac{V_{tp} - V_p}{V_p} \times 100$$

Where, V_{tp} = tapped density; V_p = bulk density.

4. Angle of repose

The improper flow of powder is due to frictional forces between the particles. These friction forces were quantified by angle of repose.

c. Evaluation of sustained release bilayer tablets

1) Weight variation

The USP weight variation test is done by weighing 20 tablets individually, calculating the average weight and comparing the individual weights to the average.

Table No 7: Weight variation Limit.

Sr. No.	Average weight of tablet (mg)	Maximum difference allowed
1.	130 or less	10
2.	130-324	7.5
3.	324<	5

2) Hardness test

The hardness of each batch of tablet was checked by using Monsanto hardness tester.

3) Friability

20 tablets were weighed and placed in the plastic chamber of Roches friabilator. The chamber was then rotated for four minutes at 25 rpm (a total of 100 revolutions). During each revolution tablets fall from a distance of 6 inches. After 100 revolutions the tablets were removed and weighed again.

4) Drug content

10 tablets were weighed from each batch and average weight is calculated. All tablets were crushed and powder equivalent to 55 mg drug was dissolved in phosphate buffer 7.4 and the volume was made up to 100 ml with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. From the stock solution, 1ml solution was taken in 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made with pH 7.4 phosphate buffers. Solution was filtered and absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 288 nm against pH 7.4 phosphate buffer as a blank. Amount of drug present in one tablet was

calculated.

d. Dissolution studies

- 1) Drug Release Studies for Immediate release layer:- The in vitro dissolution of immediate release layer was determined using USP XXIII (basket method)dissolution apparatus.
- 2) Drug Release Studies for sustained release:- The in vitro dissolution of sustained release layer was determined using USP XXIII (basket method)dissolution apparatus.
- 3) Drug Release Studies for Bilayer Tablets:- The in vitro dissolution of Propranolol bilayer tablets were determined using USP XXIII (basket method) dissolution apparatus.

Table No. 8: Details data of dissolution test.

Dissolution test apparatus	USP type II
Speed	50 rpm
Stirrer	Paddle type
Volume of medium	900 ml
Volume withdrawn	5 ml
Medium used	7.4 phosphate buffer
Temperature	37±0.5°C

e. Mathematical modelling of drug release profile

1. Zero order kinetics: When the data is plotted as cumulative % drug release versus time, if the plot is linear then the data obeys zero- order release Kinetics, with a slope equal to K_0 .
2. First order Kinetics: When the data is plotted as log cumulative % drug remaining versus time yields a straight line, indicating that the release follows first order kinetics.
3. Higuchi's model: When the data is plotted as cumulative drug release versus square root of time, yields a straight line, indicating that the drug was released by diffusion mechanism.
4. Korsmeyer equation/ Peppas's model: When the data is plotted as log of drug released versus time, yields a straight line with a slope equal to „n“ and the „K“ can be obtained from y- intercept.

f. Stability studies

The reason of stability testing is to provide evidence on how the quality of drug formulation varies with time under the influence of various environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, light. From this study we know about recommended storage condition, re-test periods and shelf-life of the drug can be established.

Stability studies are important for the following reasons.

1. This is an assurance given by the manufacturer that the patient would receive a uniform dose throughout the shelf life.
2. The drug control administration insists on manufacturers on conducting the stability studies, identity, strength, purity and quality of the drug for an extended period of time in the conditions of normal storage.
3. Stability testing prevents the possibility of marketing an unstable product. Both physical and chemical degradation of drug can result in unstable product.

Purpose of stability studies: Stability studies are done to understand how to design a product and its packaging.

Storage conditions: Stability studies were carried out at 25°C/60% and 40°C/75% RH for a specific period of 3 months for the selected formulations.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Pre-formulation studies

Characterization of propranolol HCL

1. Organoleptic Properties

Table No. 9: Organoleptic characterization of propranolol HCL.

Test	Observations
Colour	White crystalline powder
Taste	Bitter salty
Odour	odourless

2. Physical characteristic

a) Loss on Drying

Table No. 10: Loss on Drying.

Test	Specification / limits	Observations
Loss on drying	Not more than 0.2 %	0.1%

b) Angle of Repose

Table No. 11: Angle of Repose of Bulk Drug.

Sr.no.	Material	Angle of repose	Average angle Of repose
1.	Propranolol HCL	28° 37'	28° 56'
2.		29° 17'	
3.		28° 14'	

The drug belongs to good flow property.

c) Determination Bulk density and Tapped density

Table No: 12: Determination of Bulk density and Tap density.

Sr.no.	Material	Bulk Density (gm / ml)	Average Bulk Density (gm /ml)	Tapped Density (gm / ml)	Average Tapped Density (gm /cc)
1	Propranolol HCL	0.364	0.359	0.531	0.533
2.		0.358		0.536	
3.		0.357		0.532	

d) Powder Compressibility and Hausner's ratio

Materials	Compressibility index	Hausner ratio
Propranolol HCL	22.64	1.34

3. Solubility properties

1) Solubility

Solubility study of drug (PRP) was performed in 0.1N HCL, distilled water; phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and results are presented in Table.

S. No.	Solvent	Propranolol hydrochloride
1.	O.1HCL pH 1.2	138.27±0.1 mg/ml
2.	Distilled water	58.32±0.4 mg/ml
3.	Buffer pH 7.4	145.80±0.2 mg/ml

2) Ph. of the solution

The ph of the solution was found to be 3 with the help of ph meter it was Detected.

3) Melting point

S. No.	Drug	Melting point
1.	Propranolol HCL	158-164 ^{0C}

4. Partition Coefficient

The partition coefficient of the drug was calculated by using the formula:

S. No.	Drug	Partition coefficient(log P)
1.	Propranolol HCL	1.26±0.11

Amount of drug in organic layer

Partition coefficient, (k) = Amount of drug in aqueous layer / Amount of drug in organic layer. Partition coefficient is the measurement of drug's lipophilicity and its capability to cross cell membranes. It is defined as the fraction of unionized drug distributed between the organic and aqueous part at equilibrium.

5. Analytical methods

a. Standard curve of propranolol HCL (λ max)

1) Calibration curve of propranolol hydrochloride using HCL(pH1.2)

The calibration curve of propranolol HCL was prepared using 0.1N HCL pH 1.2, phosphate buffer, pH 6.8 and 7.4, by using Ultraviolet-visible (UV) spectroscopy.

Figure No: 3 UV curve of propranolol HCL using 0.1N HCL (pH 1.2)

Table No: 13 Calibration curve of propranolol HCL using 0.1N HCL (pH 1.2).

S. No	Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Absorbance
1.	0	0
2.	10	0.237
3.	20	0.429
4.	30	0.639
5.	40	0.860
6.	50	1.073

Figure No.: 4 Standard curve of propranolol HCL using 0.1N HCL (pH 1.2)

1. Calibration curve of propranolol hydrochloride using HCL (pH 1.2)

The absorbance was determined at 288 nm for different concentrations in the range of 10, 20,

30, 40, 50 µg/ml.

Figure No: 5 UV curve of propranolol HCL using phosphate buffer (pH 6.8).

Table No 14: Calibration curve of propranolol HCL using phosphate buffer (pH 6.8)

S. No.	Concentration µg/ml	Absorbance
1.	0	0
2.	10	0.240
3.	20	0.395
4.	30	0.598
5.	40	0.794
6.	50	0.977

Figure No: 6 Standard curve of propranolol HCL using phosphate buffer (pH 6.8).

2. Calibration curve of propranolol HCL using phosphate buffer (pH 7.4)

The calibration curve of propranolol HCL was prepared in phosphate buffer, pH7.4 by using UV spectroscopy. The absorbance was determined at 288nm for different concentrations in the range of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 μ g/ml. A high degree of correlation ($R^2 = 0.999$) was observed between the concentration of the drug solution and their respective absorbance obtained.

Figure No: 7 UV curve of propranolol HCL using phosphate buffer (pH 7.4)

Table No 15: Calibration curve of propranolol HCL using phosphate buffer (pH 7.4).

S. No.	Concentration μ g/ml	Absorbance
1.	0	0
2.	10	0.217
3.	20	0.428
4.	30	0.641
5.	40	0.835
6.	50	1.042

Figure No 8: Standard curve of propranolol HCL using phosphate buffer (pH 7.4).

6. Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy

1) FTIR of propranolol HCL

The Infrared spectroscopy studies were conducted for pure drug (PRP). The main peaks of propranolol HCL, C₁₆H₂₁NO₂ HCL, were at 3274 cm⁻¹, 2803 cm⁻¹, 1265 cm⁻¹, and 823 cm⁻¹ represented secondary hydroxyl group, secondary amine group, aryl alkyl ether, and substituted naphthalene, respectively. The FTIR spectra of propranolol HCL.

Table No 16: FTIR interpretation of propranolol HCL.

FTIR range of peak(cm-1)	Presence of functional groups in PRP
3274.30	Secondary Hydroxyl group
2803.02-2706.16	Secondary Amine
2494.38-2362.55	C=C stretching
1686.31 Sharp	Sharp N-H bending
1449.58	C-C Stretching
1265.32-1237.56 Sharp	Aryl alkyl ether
1168.29-1102.39 Sharp	Alkyl halide
957.65	=C-H Bend
899.25-823.97 Sharp	C-H of Aromatic
796.11-766.16 Sharp A	Substituted naphthalene

Figure No: 9 FTIR spectra of propranolol HCL.

Figure No. 10: FTIR spectra of propranolol (a), propranolol with ethyl cellulose (b), propranolol with HPMC K15(c), Propranolol with HPMC K100 (d).

From the results, it was concluded that there was no interference of the functional group as the principle peaks of the PRP were found to be unaltered in the drug- polymer physical mixtures, indicating that they were compatible chemically. The spectrum confirmed that there is no significant change in the chemical integrity of the drug.

7. Prepared Bi-layer sustained release Anti-hypertensive Tablet

Fig No. 11: Prepared Bi-layer sustained release Anti-hypertensive Tablets.

8. Evaluation Parameters

a) Evaluation of powder blended characteristics of Bilayer tablet formulation of Propranolol For each type of formulation, blends of propranolol and other excipients were prepared and evaluated for various parameters such as bulk density, tapped density, Carr's compressibility index, Hausner's ratio and angle of repose. Bulk density was found in the range of 0.2785 ± 1.2 - 0.3240 ± 1.4 for immediate release & 0.2237 - 0.3642 g/cm³ for sustained

release. And the tapped density between 0.3756 ± 0.0014 0.4500 ± 0.0012 for IR & $0.3810 - 0.4880 \text{g/cm}^3$ for sustained release indicating both parameters were found to be within the limits. Using the above two density data, Carr's compressibility index were calculated. The compressibility index and Hausner's ratio was found in the range of 9.21 12.54 fir IR & 7.2718.42 % and 1.0531.24 for sustained release respectively indicating that all powder blends showed excellent to acceptable flow properties. The flow property of all powder blends was better explained from angle of repose. The angle of repose was found in the range of $25.25 \pm 0.23 - 27.14 \pm 0.14$ fir IR & $25.33 - 31.43^\circ$ for sustained release. The results of angle of repose showed all powder blends exhibited good to acceptable flow property. The results of precompression parameters are shown in table no: 17

Table No. 17: Evaluation parameters of pre-formulation characteristics of powder blend.

Formulations Number	Bulk Density (gm/cc)	Tapped Density (gm/cc)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner's Ratio	Angle of Repose (θ)
IR 1	0.2785 ± 1.2	0.4500 ± 0.0012	10.21 ± 0.325	1.035 ± 0.0025	26.85 ± 0.14
IR 2	0.2883 ± 1.8	0.3756 ± 0.0014	9.21 ± 0.0456	1.231 ± 0.0014	27.14 ± 0.68
IR 3	0.3240 ± 1.4	0.3932 ± 0.00021	12.54 ± 147	1.0512 ± 0.0056	25.25 ± 0.23
F1	0.2237 ± 1.1	0.3810 ± 0.0045	7.27 ± 0.659	1.177 ± 0.0076	29.73 ± 0.41
F2	0.3642 ± 1.8	0.4120 ± 0.0026	7.58 ± 0.514	1.053 ± 0.0060	25.33 ± 0.63
F3	0.2836 ± 1.0	0.4120 ± 0.005	7.43 ± 0.760	1.059 ± 0.0088	28.44 ± 0.35
F4	0.2090 ± 1.6	0.4270 ± 0.0037	13.78 ± 0.386	1.073 ± 0.0053	27.48 ± 0.52
F5	0.3457 ± 0.8	0.4600 ± 0.0024	17.31 ± 0.794	1.224 ± 0.011	31.34 ± 0.13
F6	0.2882 ± 1.9	0.4880 ± 0.0065	18.42 ± 0.120	1.24 ± 0.0020	28.26 ± 0.43
F7	0.2240 ± 0.3	0.3923 ± 0.0023	8.56 ± 0.230	1.054 ± 0.0023	26.54 ± 0.12
F8	0.2536 ± 1.5	0.4498 ± 0.0048	11.65 ± 0.198	1.211 ± 0.0012	30.47 ± 0.54
F9	0.3285 ± 1.2	0.4025 ± 0.0014	14.21 ± 0.114	1.056 ± 0.0077	26.11 ± 0.14

2. Post-compression parameters

Table No: 18: Post-compression parameter for immediate release tablet.

Formulation	Diameter (mm) \pm SD	Thickness (mm) \pm SD	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Disintegration time	Drug Content (%)
IR 1	4.25 ± 0.014	1.2 ± 0.065	99.45 ± 0.17	3.7 ± 0.06	0.12 ± 0.07	30 ± 0.10	98.25 ± 0.02
IR 2	3.95 ± 0.016	1.6 ± 0.041	99.25 ± 0.14	3.8 ± 0.32	0.14 ± 0.10	25 ± 0.14	97.65 ± 0.14
IR 3	5.41 ± 0.19	2.1 ± 0.014	100.12 ± 0.014	3.7 ± 0.74	0.19 ± 0.14	15 ± 0.65	99.25 ± 0.19

From the above observation it was found that IR 3 shows good result. So it will be used as optimized batch.

Table No 19: standard physical tests for Bilayer tablets.

Formulation	Diameter (mm)± SD	Thickness (mm)± SD	Weight variation(mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability(%)	Drug content (%)
F1	7.82±0.012	3.9±0.09	250.89±0.12	7.3±0.04	0.64±0.007	97.75±0.025
F2	7.80±0.002	4.0±0.02	253.88±0.60	7.8±0.03	0.52±0.005	98.25±0.044
F3	7.85±0.007	4.2±0.01	251.12±0.52	8.0±0.07	0.58±0.031	98.31±0.037
F4	7.84±0.022	3.9±0.07	249.81±0.13	6.5±0.04	0.72±0.016	96.23±0.025
F5	8.0±0.015	4.0±0.04	250.80±0.32	6.8±0.08	0.42±0.09	98.37±0.058
F6	7.94±0.010	3.8±0.09	248.92±0.44	7.1±0.03	0.42±0.01	99.12±0.23
F7	7.88±0.021	3.8±0.01	247.69±0.55	6.6±0.01	0.40±0.002	97.61±0.08
F8	8.0±0.014	4.0±0.09	250.01±0.14	7.2±0.02	0.56±0.025	98.56±0.22
F9	7.89±0.047	4.1±0.01	252.12±0.01	7.1±0.01	0.71±0.012	99.67±0.07

Discussion about the physical parameters such as

- A. Thickness of tablets
- B. Hardness
- C. Friability
- D. Weight Variation
- E. Drug content

A. Tablet thickness

The average thickness for each formulation was found to be between 3.8 and 4.2 mm, which is within the permitted limit of deviation, or 5% of the standard value. Additionally, all pill formulations had crown diameters between 8.0 and 7.8 mm.

B. Hardness

The hardness test was carried out using a "Monsanto hardness tester."

The average hardness of each formulation ranges from 6.0 to 8.0 kg/cm².

C. Friability

The average percentage friability for all formulations was determined to be between 0.40% and 0.72%, which is discovered to be less than 1%, or inside the pharmacopoeial limit. Thus, F4 had the highest friability of 0.72%, while F7 had the lowest friability of 0.40.7%.

D. Test for weight variation

The weight variation for all formulations, which was found to be between 249.92 and 253.88 mg. Since the weight variation percentage was within the pharmacopoeial limitations (<5%), all of the prepared tablets passed the weight variation test. It was discovered that all of the tablets had consistent weights with minimal standard deviation values.

E. Content of Drugs

The medication content % for formulations F1 through F9 was found to be between 96.23% w/w and 99.67% w/w. It complies with official specifications.

9. In-vitro Drug release studies

Investigation of Propranolol's immediate release layer in vitro. Showed the release profile of propranolol from several batches of prepared tablets. All of the immediate release layer batches demonstrated drug release within 20 to 30 minutes, according to the findings of in-vitro dissolution tests. However, the formulation IR3 was deemed the best batch to be included in the bilayer tablet formulation since it demonstrated the highest quantity of drug release, $99.10 \pm 0.95\%$, within 15 minutes in an immediate release manner. According to the findings of invitro drug release tests, the release rate of propranolol rose when the concentration of S.S.G. climbed from 5% to 10%. This is due to the reason that increased concentration of disintegrant lead to decreased disintegration time and thus increased release of Propranolol.

Table No. 20: In-vitro disintegration data for IR-1, IR-2, and IR-3 Formulation.

SR. No	Time (min)	IR-1	IR-2	IR-3
	0	0	0	0
1.	5	25.32 ± 0.4	39.40 ± 0.10	49.40 ± 0.20
2.	10	40.50 ± 0.10	50.13 ± 1.4	75.30 ± 0.21
3.	15	62.90 ± 0.12	71.23 ± 0.41	99.10 ± 0.95
4.	20	78.90 ± 0.21	84.54 ± 0.10	
5.	25	89.40 ± 0.40	97.90 ± 10	
6.	30	98.10 ± 0.11		

Figure No: 12 In-vitro disintegration data for IR-1, IR-2, and IR-3 Formulation.

Table No 21: In-vitro dissolution data of F4, F5, and F6 Formulation.

Time(hrs.)	Cumulative percent drug release		
	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0
1	25.72±0.10	23.81±0.10	21.26±0.8
2	29.99±0.18	28.10±0.7	25.25±0.12
3	41.54±0.9	35.23±0.1	28.10±0.8
4	58.74±0.12	42.12±0.8	32.12±0.12
5	68.72±0.8	50.23±0.1	40.40±0.5
6	81.57±0.12	65.10±0.23	52.13±0.12
7	95.19±0.10	76.70±0.8	61.23±0.8
8	97.17±0.8	84.17±0.6	65.10±0.2
9	98.13±0.4	89.3±0.2	70.53±0.13
10	98.13±0.6	95.2±0.14	78.13±0.5
11		97.5±0.5	85.20±0.1
12			89.54±0.5
13			95.23±0.24
14			98.81±0.9

Figure No. 13 In-vitro dissolution profile of F4, F5 and F6 formulation.

Table No 22: In-vitro dissolution data of F7, F8 and F9 Formulation.

Time (hrs.)	Cumulative percent drug release		
	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0
1	22.94±0.08	19.12±0.3	18.14±0.8
2	29.91±0.11	25.87±0.15	23.25±0.7
3	50.13±0.12	38.56±0.10	31.12±0.3
4	55.6±0.42	47.41±0.6	38.62±0.95
5	62.4±0.13	56.96±0.15	46.93±0.17
6	70.13±0.12	68.92±0.14	57.81±0.9
7	78.95±0.14	75.53±0.12	65.10±0.11
8	82.61±0.66	86.66±0.94	72.5±0.6
9	97.26±0.13	95.98±0.1	81.62±0.7
10	97.41±0.78	97.49±0.18	91.17±0.18
11		98.82±0.33	95.62±0.8
12			97.62±0.94
13			98.03±0.17
14			99.67±0.1

Figure 14: F7, F8, and F9 formulations' in vitro dissolution profiles.

The cumulative percent drug released vs. time was plotted to examine the release of propranolol hydrochloride from the produced formulations. A basic visual examination of the plot reveals an initial burst effect. During the first fifteen minutes of the dissolution testing, more than thirty percent of the propranolol hydrochloride from all the formulations was released. The formulation's immediate release layer is responsible for the initial high level of propranolol hydrochloride release. For twelve hours, further propranolol. Because the hydrophobic ethylcellulose on the tablet's surface prevents solvent molecules from penetrating the system, EC decreases drug release; in other words, the permeability of the bilayer structure controls the rate of release. Propranolol hydrochloride release slows down as ethylcellulose content rises demonstrates that the EC 1:0.5 formulation was unable to maintain the release for more than seven hours. Over the course of the 12hour test,

formulations EC 1:1 and EC 1:1.5 demonstrated the intended release profile. In light of the minimal quantity of ethylcellulose needed to maintain the release for a duration of 12 hours, formulation EC 1:1 was chosen as the optimal formulation. In light of the minimal quantity of ethylcellulose needed to maintain the release for a duration of 12 hours, formulation EC 1:1 was chosen as the optimal formulation. Similarly, HPMC K15 M (HPMC K15 M 1:0.5 and HPMC K15 1:1) and HPMC 100 (HPMC 100 1:0.5 and HPMC 100 1:1) formulations failed to maintain drug release for the intended 12hour duration HPMC K15 M 1:1.5 and HPMC 100 1:1.5, on the other hand, could maintain the release for 12 hours. As a result, Batch F9 was chosen as an optimal formulation. For the final two, the computed regression coefficients for the Higuchi, zero order, and first order models were 0.98462409, 0.9582674, and 0.882118879, respectively. Thus, the release appears to be appropriate for the Higuchi model.

10. Release Kinetics

Regression coefficients were computed by fitting the invitro drug release data for PRP sustained release bilayer tablet formulations made using the direct compression approach to various kinetic models. Table No. displays the regression values and rate constants for the PRP sustained release bilayer matrix tablet formulations made by direct compression. The improved batch F-9's release kinetics are listed below.

Table No: 23 Drug release kinetic studies of Optimized Batch F9 for sustained release bilayer tablets.

	Zero Order	First Order	Hixon Crowell	korse meyer peppas model	HiguchiPlot
R2 Value	0.9582674	0.75191007	0.882118879	0.334086587	0.98462409
Slope	0.119830952	0.00146414	0.009370415	0.727849504	0.24081498
Intercept	16.147	1.06591408	3.738612833	-1.965184889	2.88978641

Fig. no. 15 Drug release kinetic studies of Optimized Batch F-9.

11. Stability studies

Stability tests conducted over a three month period showed no discernible medication deterioration. As a result, the produced formulations were stable both chemically and physically. The stability study results were compiled into a table. no.

Table No: 24 Results of stability studies for formulation F9 stored at 25°C/60% and 45°C/75%RH.

Storage period	Stored at 25°C/60% RH			Stored at 45°C/75% RH		
	Formulation F9			Formulation F9		
	Hardness Kg/cm ²	% friability	% Drug content	Hardness Kg/cm ²	% friability	% Drug content
Initial	7.1±0.06	0.71±0.2	99.67±0.5	7.1±0.06	0.71±0.2	99.67±0.5
After 15 days	6.5±0.16	0.57±0.3	99.6±0.1	6.4±0.11	0.55±0.1	97.5±0.3
After 30 days	6.3±0.21	0.60±0.4	99.4±0.2	6.2±0.21	0.59±0.1	97.2±0.3
After 45 days	6.2±0.15	0.62±0.3	98.3±0.6	6.0±0.23	0.61±0.3	97.0±0.3

Fig No: 16 Results of stability studies for formulation F9 stored at 25°C/60% and 45°C/75%RH.

VII. CONCLUSION

As a beta blocker, propranolol reduces blood pressure by blocking the activity of norepinephrine (noradrenaline) and epinephrine (adrenaline) at both β_1 - and β_2 -adrenergic receptors. The current study's goal was to find out if propranolol release from bilayer tablets made with various polymer concentrations could be sustained. After the powder mixes were crushed into tablets, postcompression parameters such as weight fluctuation, thickness,

hardness, friability, and drug content were assessed. Every formulation batch produced results that were satisfactory. The outcome can lead to the following conclusions. All formulations' preformulation examinations, including angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Hausnes ratio, and Carr's index, were found to be within determined to be within the typical bounds. FTIR analyses showed that the medication and other excipients did not interact chemically. After the powder mixes were crushed into tablets, postcompression parameters such as weight fluctuation, thickness, hardness, friability, and drug content were assessed. Every formulation batch produced results that were satisfactory. For a duration of 24 hours, the invitro drug release was investigated using USP Type II dissolution apparatus in both intestinal fluid and simulated stomach fluid. The drug release was sustained over a 24hour period by formulations with higher concentrations of HPMC K15 M, or F6 (99.12%), and HPMC K 100, or F9 (99.67%). The drug release in vitro is first order, suggesting that the mechanism of drug release may be non-Fickian. According to stability studies, the tablet formulations remained stable for the duration of the stability period. It was determined that the polymer is a key component in the formulation of propranolol sustain release bilayer tablets. Ultimately, the study found that when the bilayer tablet had a larger concentration of polymers, the drug release was reduced.

REFERENCES

1. Ratnaparkhi MP, Gupta Jyoti P. Sustained release oral drug delivery system-an overview. *International Journal of Pharma Research and Review*, 2013; 2(3): 11-12
2. Kar RK, Mohapatra S, BarikBB. Design and characterization of controlled release matrix tablets of Zidovudine. *Asian J. Pharm. Cli. Res.*, 2009; 2: 54-6.
3. D. Jadhav, R. Kharat, S. Jadhav and M. Patil. Design and evaluation of sustained release matrix tablets of propranolol hydrochloride. *Indo Am. J. Pharmaceutical Res.*, 2015; 5: 1109-1117.
4. Lachman L, Liberman HA, Kang JL. *The theory and practice of industrial pharmacy*. 3rd edition: Varghese Publishing house, Mumbai, 1987; 296-300.
5. Robinson JR, Lee HL. *Controlled drug delivery fundamentals and applications*, 2nd edition: Marcel Dekker Inc New York, 1987; 739.
6. Ho WH, Lee HL. *Sustained drug delivery fundamentals and applications: design and fabrication of oral controlled release drug delivery system*, 2nd edition: Marcel Dekker Inc, New York, 1987; 373-374.
7. Jain NK. *Controlled and novel drug delivery*. 1st edition: CBS publisher and Distributor,

- New Delhi, 1997; 20-22.
7. Brahmkar DM, Jaiswal SB. Biopharmaceutics and Pharmacokinetics-Treatise. 3ed edition: Vallabh Prakashan, New Delhi, 2015; 402-403.
 8. James Swarbrick, James C. Boylan, Banker GS, Rhodes CT. Sustained and controlled release drug delivery systems", Modern Pharmaceutics, 4th edition: Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 2002; 752-753.
 9. Robinson J, Lee VH. Controlled drug delivery: Fundamentals and applications. 2nd edition: CRC Press, New York, 2002; 903-905.
 10. Wise DL. Handbook of pharmaceutical controlled release technology. 1st edition: Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 2005; 5-7.
 11. Jantzen GM, Robinson JR. Sustained and controlled-release drug delivery systems. Modern Pharmaceutics. 3rd edition: Marcel Dekker, Inc., 1995; 72: 575-578.
 12. Patel Harinsh, Dhruv R, Panchal, Patel U, Brahmhatt T, Suthar M. Matrix type drug delivery system a review. Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Bio-Scientific Research, 2011; 1(3): 143-147.
 13. Vyas SP, Khar RK. Proteins and peptides delivery considerations. Controlled drug delivery concepts and advances. 1st edition, CBS publisher and Distributor New Delhi, 2002; 411-412.
 14. Tripathi KD. Essentials of medical pharmacology. 6th edition: Jaypee Brothers New Delhi, 2009; 539-540.
 15. Pattan SR, Zanwar AO, Wabale NB, Shetkar UB. Review articles on scope and need of combination of antihypertensive drugs, Indian drugs, 2012; 49(05): 5-6.
 16. Finkel R, Clark MA, Cubeddu LX. Pharmacology. 4th edition: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, Florida, 2009; 216-217.
 17. Haddad LM, Winchester JF. Clinical Management of Poisoning and Drug Overdose. 2nd edition: 1990; 1315-1316.
 18. Ekwall B, Clemedson C, Crafoord B, Ekwall B, Hallander S, Walum E, Bondesson I. Evaluation of acute systemic toxicity. Part V. Rodent and human toxicity data for the 50 referencechemicals, Alternative to laboratory animals: ATLA, 1998; 26: 571-616.
 19. Baselt RC, Cravey RH. Disposition of toxic drugs and chemicals in man. 4th edition: Chemical Toxicology Institute, Foster City, USA, 1995; 661-665.
 20. Odou P, Ferrari N, Barthelemy C, Brique S, Lhermitte M, Vincent A, Libersa C, Robert H. Grapefruit juice–nifedipine interaction: possible involvement of several mechanisms. Journal of Clinical Pharmacy and Therapeutics, 2005; 30(2): 153-154.

21. Poole-Wilson PA, Kirwan BA, Vokó Z, de Brouwer S, van Dalen FJ, Lubsen J. Action investigators. Safety of nifedipine gits instable angina: the action trial. *Cardiovascular Drugs and Therapy*, 2006; 20(1): 45-46.
22. Takahashi D, Oyunzul L, Onoue S, Ito Y, Uchida S, Simsek R, Gunduz MG, Safak C, Yamada.
23. S. Structure–activity relationships of receptor binding of 1, 4-dihydropyridine derivatives. *Biological and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*, 2008; 31(3): 473-475.
24. Gerard T. Tamarind gum in hand book of water soluble gums and resins. McGraw-Hill Book Co, 1980; 12; 1-23.
25. Rao PS, Ghosh TP, Krishna S. Extraction and purification of tamarind seed polysaccharide. *Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research*, 1946; 4: 705.
26. Martindale, The Extra Pharmacopoeia, 31sted. The Pharmaceutical Press, London; 1996: 936– 937.
27. Shiyani B et al, Gattani S et al, Surana S. et al. Formulation and evaluation of bi-layer tablet of Metoclopramide hydrochloride and Ibuprofen. *AAPS Pharm. Sci. Tech.*, 2008; 9(3): 818-27. Pranjali Kumar Singh et al, Sanjoo Kumar et al Bilayer and Floating Bioadhesive Tablets: Innovative approach to Gastroretention, *Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics*; 2011; 1(1): 32-35.
28. Kulkarni A et al, Bhatia M. et al, Development and evaluation of bilayer floating tablets of atenolol and lovastatin for biphasic release profile.
29. Nirmal J et al, Saisivam S et al, Peddanna C et al, Muralidharan S et al, Nagarajan M et al, Bilayer tablets of atorvastatin calcium and nicotinic acid: formulation and evaluation. *Chem. Pharm., Bull.* 2008; 56: 1455–1458, 26- 102-1PB.
30. Chein, Y. W. Oral drug delivery and delivery systems. *Novel drug delivery systems*, 1992; 50: 139-177.
31. Galey, W. R., Lonsdale, H. K., & Nacht, S. The in vitro permeability of skin and buccal mucosa to selected drugs and tritiated water. *Journal of investigative dermatology*, 1976; 67(6): 713-717.
32. Siddiqui, M. N., Garg, G., & Sharma, P. K. A short review on “A novel approach in oral fast dissolving drug delivery system and their patents”. *Adv. Biol. Res.*, 2011; 5(6): 291-303.
33. Sharma, S., Gupta, G., Bala, R., Sharma, N., Seth, N., & Goswami, J. (2008). Orodispersible tablet: a review. *Pharmainfo. net. html*, 6(5).